

Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning for Traffic Signal Optimization with Swarm of Drones

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1 Methodology

This section presents a comprehensive explanation of the methodology and the relationships between its components. The simulation undergoes two main phases: the training and the evaluation phase, as shown in Fig. 1. In the training phase, the simulation trains a multi agent DQN using real-time traffic data generated from a simulation of Namur, Belgium, with the aim of minimizing the remaining number of vehicles at four intersections with varying road geometries and traffic signal phase configurations. The multi agent DQN interacts with the Vissim environment, receiving the resulting states that indicate the impact of its actions and the corresponding rewards to guide learning and build a history set. Finally, the main goal of the multi agent DQN is to define a policy based on historical traffic data that maps the number of vehicles to optimal green light durations, thereby efficiently reducing congestion on interconnected roads between intersections. During the evaluation phase, we assess the performance of the trained multi agent DQN using the swarm of drone within the Vissim simulation environment. The drones are deployed to collect real-time data based on predefined path planning, which serve as input states for the network to select greedy actions that maximize the expected reward. However, because Vissim does not natively support drone flight simulation, each road segment in the Vissim environment is discretized into fixed-length cells. The vehicle counts within these sub-cells, which form a cellular representation of the road network in the Python environment, are continuously updated based on the traffic flows generated by the Vissim model. This dynamically updated cellular map is then used to guide drone navigation and enables systematic, cell-by-cell traffic data collection by drones. To solve communication problems between the drones and the traffic lights, fixed meeting points have been assigned where drones transmit recent collected data to the traffic lights and receive traffic related data about regions outside their paths. The methodology enables each agent to access information from adjacent agents, supporting synchronized operation within the distributed network. Finally, the optimal green time durations are implemented in Vissim to evaluate their performance.

Figure 1: Namur simulated network in Vissim.

2 Namur Simulation Model

The simulated roads are represented in dark gray, with six traffic inflows connected to the main circular boundary of the layout to model traffic entering the city center as shown in Fig. 2. Vissim is used to simulate traffic dynamics, generate real time data to train the DQN, and evaluate the performance of traffic light signaling systems in response to varying levels of traffic congestion. In the training process, traffic data generated by Vissim, such as vehicle numbers, is used to train the DQN. The model receives actions and responds with the resulting states and their respective action rewards. Due to the limitations of Vissim in supporting drone based observation, a discrete cellular map is designed to represent traffic data by distributing vehicle counts across subcells. The lengths of the Vissim roads, including Boulevard de Chiny, Rue Godefroid, and Boulevard Ernest Melot, are approximately 360 m, 280 m, and 320 m, respectively. The map divides each road segment into multiple subcells, each measuring 20 meters, covering all directions of traffic flow.

3 Action Space

We define the minimum and maximum duration of the green traffic light as $S_{\{i,k,green\}min}$ and $S_{\{i,k,green\}max}$ for each lanes, respectively. The sum of the green light duration for all traffic lights at an intersection $S_{\{i,k,green\}}$ where $k = \{w, e, s, n\}$ is considered as cycle time as follows:

$$C = \sum_{k=w}^n S_{\{i,k,green\}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: Namur simulated network in Vissim.

4 Path Planning for Drones

The camera is oriented in a nadir (downward facing) position of the drones with a fixed angle of view. In the cellular model, to ensure complete coverage of a single cell, the drones should fly at specific flight altitudes as follows:

$$h = \frac{cell_{dimension}}{2 \cdot \tan(\theta/2)} \quad (2)$$

Where h is the required flight altitude for the drones to fully cover an area with the cell dimension ($cell_{dimension}$) and θ is the camera's field of view angle. $cell_{dimension}$ is defined as a 20×20 meter rectangle, then a flight altitude of 10 meters is necessary to achieve complete drone coverage.

5 Result

The statistical results, including the mean value (MV), standard deviation (SD), and confidence intervals (CI), are shown in Tab. 1, confirm that the DQN controller using a swarm of drones outperforms both the DQN controller using fixed cameras and the fixed-time control strategy.

Table 1: Statistical Result.

Control Strategy	Road	MV	SD	CI
DQN and Swarm of Drone	West/East	12.03	9.84	[8.42, 15.64]
	South	4.42	3.72	[3.05, 5.78]
DQN and Fix Camera	West/East	15.45	7.90	[12.55, 18.35]
	South	17.45	7.16	[14.83, 20.08]
Fix Control	West/East	15.68	7.28	[13.01, 18.35]
	South	23.90	2.43	[23.01, 24.79]